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*The Shifting Landscape of European
Company Law*

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The Shifting Landscape of European Company Law

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Abstract

The European Union (EU) has recently placed itself at the vanguard of company law reform, first under the heading of ‘corporate sustainability’ and more recently still as part of its aim to boost the competitiveness of the EU economy. The movement between these policy objectives has created a rapidly evolving and dynamic European company law landscape. For example, the major corporate sustainability laws, the Corporate Sustainability Reporting and Due Diligence Directives, despite being only recently introduced, are now to be simplified and reduced in scope by Omnibus I. In addition, the Commission plans to introduce a range of positive interventions to boost the competitiveness of European companies, most notably through a 28th regime i.e. an EU specific business code. The aim of the regime would be to form a truly European company that can transcend the fragmented landscape of 27 different national frameworks and the barriers this creates within the single market. However, similar initiatives have been attempted before with limited success. This working paper discusses the recent developments in European company law, locates them within the area’s historical development and offers some analysis of the difficulties involved in the reform of European company law.

Introduction

A pressing issue of our time is the how to align the interests of companies with the interests of society.² Companies, while providing crucial economic benefits to society, also impose costs in the form of environmental damage, harms to stakeholders and human rights abuses. This is not a new observation and many initiatives have attempted to reduce the harms and negative externalities³ of business, for example, through human rights principles, corporate governance codes and through market incentives.⁴ For legal initiatives, the difficulty lies in finding the appropriate balance between reducing these harms while continuing to facilitate economically

¹ *A revised version of this working paper is available as the introductory chapter to my book *The Societal Company: Sustainability, Shareholder Value, and European Company Law* (Hart, 2025) <https://www.bloomsbury.com/in/societal-company-9781509977765/>. Many thanks to Prof. Federico Fabbrini and the team at the Dublin European Law Institute for facilitating the publication of this working paper and their support of my work on European company and commercial law.

² For one example of the extensive scholarship on this point see E. Ferran and P. Schilling de Carvalho, ‘Reconciling Shareholder Primacy and the Interests of People and Planet’ (2025) *Law Quarterly Review* available at https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5084134.

³ Referring to the adverse impact of economic activities on the welfare of those uninvolved in these activities.

⁴ I principally refer here to the rise of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) investing, see M. Barzuza, Q. Curtis and D. Webber, ‘Shareholder Value(s): Index Fund ESG Activism and the New Millennial Corporate Governance’ (2020) 93 *Southern California Law Review* 1243.

productive and innovative business. In an attempt to find this balance, the European Union (EU) has been at the forefront of company law reform, first under the heading of ‘corporate sustainability’ and more recently still under the label of ‘competitiveness’.

The EU’s reform of company law began in 2019 with the publication of the European Green Deal⁵ which emphasised the importance of company law and stated that sustainability should be ‘embedded into the corporate governance framework’.⁶ A more detailed description was set out in the Commission’s Action Plan for Financing Sustainable Growth⁷ which made specific reference to corporate sustainability reporting and due diligence obligations.⁸ Other reports followed on sustainable finance,⁹ supply chains¹⁰ and sustainable corporate governance.¹¹ The outcome of these reports and the policy focus on sustainability was the enactment of the Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR),¹² the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)¹³ and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD).¹⁴

These Directives were landmark initiatives in many respects. First, they approached company law - which traditionally focused on enabling business and governing participant relationships¹⁵ - from the perspective of protecting the environment and upholding human rights standards. Second, they introduced mandatory rules around relatively novel *legal* concepts of reporting and due diligence.¹⁶ Third, the CSDDD, by introducing civil liability for harms arising from a company’s supply chain¹⁷ seemed to undermine company law’s core assumption that every company is a separate person which is not responsible for the actions of other companies.¹⁸ Hence, the EU, through these sustainability Directives, was making real changes to the scope and objectives of corporate law.

⁵ Communication from the Commission on the European Green Deal, (2019) available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52019DC0640>.

⁶ *Ibid*, [2.2.1].

⁷ The European Commission, *Action Plan: Financing Sustainable Growth* (2018) available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52018DC0097>.

⁸ *Ibid*, 11.

⁹ EU High Level Group on Sustainable Finance, ‘Sustainable Financing a European Economy’ (2018) available at https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/170713-sustainable-finance-report_en.pdf.

¹⁰ British Institute of International and Comparative Law, ‘Study on Due Diligence Requirements Through the Supply Chain’ (2020) available at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/8ba0a8fd-4c83-11ea-b8b7-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>.

¹¹ EY, *Study on Directors’ Duties and Sustainable Corporate Governance* (2020) available at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/e47928a2-d20b-11ea-adf7-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>.

¹² Regulation (EU) 2019/2088 [2019] OJ L 317/1.

¹³ Directive (EU) 2022/2464 [2022] OJ L 322/15.

¹⁴ Directive (EU) 2024/1760 [2024] OJ L, 2024/1760.

¹⁵ For example, much of company law aims to create a framework for the cooperation between shareholders, directors, employees and creditors.

¹⁶ While reporting and corporate due diligence have long been elements of corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices and discussed at length in the UN’s Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, the movement from principles to mandatory law is a relatively new development.

¹⁷ Made up of either subsidiaries or contractual partners.

¹⁸ This remains true even if several companies have a common share ownership structure or if they function as one business organisation. There are exceptions to this principle, but they are narrowly construed, see chapter 5, *The Societal Company* (n 1).

However, in 2024, the EU signalled a policy reversal, moving away from sustainability focused regulation and toward a creating legal framework that enabled European business. The process started with reports by Enrico Letta¹⁹ and Mario Draghi²⁰ which emphasised the need for Europe to create a regulatory landscape that facilitates competitiveness and resilience. The Draghi report noted that the regulatory burden on European companies is high compared to other jurisdictions²¹ and expressed concerns at the ‘innovation gap’ between Europe, China and the US.²² In the Budapest Declaration on European Competitiveness, the European Council endorsed Draghi’s report describing it as a ‘wake up call’ and expressing an intention to ‘urgently close the innovation and productivity gap’.²³ More specifically, the declaration called for ‘a simplification revolution, ensuring a clear, simple and smart regulatory framework for businesses and drastically reducing administrative, regulatory and reporting burdens’ and that the EU ‘must adopt an enabling mindset’.²⁴ These principles were again emphasised in the Commission’s Competitiveness Compass.²⁵ This policy shift led to the Omnibus I Proposal²⁶ which set out to simplify the corporate sustainability framework. The Omnibus noted the new and difficult context in which EU businesses are operating caused by higher energy costs, the rise of trade tensions and the impact of the comparatively stringent EU corporate sustainability rules. The Omnibus also emphasised that the ability of the EU to preserve and protect its values depends on the capacity of its economy to adapt and compete in an unstable and potentially hostile geopolitical environment. Based on these concerns, the proposal aimed to simplify and streamline the regulatory framework created by the CSRD and the CSDDD. However, the EU are not limiting their competitiveness focus to deregulation, but plan on positive interventions such as through the 28th regime for innovative companies.²⁷

This brief introduction demonstrates that the EU’s attempt to reform its company law framework have not been straightforward as policy priorities have shifted from sustainability to competitiveness. This working paper discusses these recent developments and offers some analysis of the difficulties involved in the reform of European company law. Section 1 sets out the classical theoretical principles on which company law rests and how EU law has traditionally followed these principles. Section 2 provides a brief description of the EU’s corporate sustainability reforms which introduced rules on corporate reporting and due

¹⁹ E. Letta, ‘Much More than A Market’ (2024) available at <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/ny3j24sm/much-more-than-a-market-report-by-enrico-letta.pdf>

²⁰ M. Draghi, ‘The Future of European Competitiveness’ (2024) available at https://commission.europa.eu/topics/eu-competitiveness/draghi-report_en#paragraph_47059.

²¹ *ibid* 69.

²² *ibid* 6.

²³ Budapest Declaration on the New European Competitiveness Deal (2024) available at <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/11/08/the-budapest-declaration/>.

²⁴ *ibid* [4].

²⁵ European Commission, A Competitiveness Compass for the EU (2025) available at https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/10017eb1-4722-4333-add2-e0ed18105a34_en?filename=Communication_1.pdf

²⁶ European Commission, ‘Omnibus I’ (2025) available at https://commission.europa.eu/publications/omnibus-i_en.

²⁷ [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2025/779233/EPRS_BRI\(2025\)779233_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2025/779233/EPRS_BRI(2025)779233_EN.pdf)

diligence. Section 3 sets out the changes introduced by the recently agreed Omnibus and reflects on what recent developments might tell us about the future of European company law reform.

1) The Classical Model of Company Law

The theory guiding company law, at least in the Anglo-American and European traditions,²⁸ is that the best way for company law to promote the interests of society is by providing a framework that facilitates the efficient organisation and operation of business.²⁹ This framework lowers the risks and costs of business³⁰ and in so doing enables the creation and operation of efficient companies which advance society's interests by, for example, offering desirable goods and services, engaging in research and development, providing employment which ultimately lead toward a competitive and prosperous economy. A crucial dimension of the theory is the acknowledgement that companies can and do cause negative externalities but that these are best addressed by other areas of law. Hence, under this view, as Friedman famously declared, the *social* responsibility of business is to make profit within the rules of the game.³¹

The intellectual foundation of this facilitative model is based on a description of the company as a nexus of contracts whose efficiency is derived from its orientation toward shareholder value.³² The nexus of contracts model reduces the company to a series of contractual rights and obligations between parties where shareholders stand out as a unique constituent given they did not expressly bargain for their position but instead claim what is left after all other contractual obligations have been satisfied i.e. they claim the residual. Hence, shareholders bear the most risk and have a homogeneous interest in maximising this residual.³³ This makes them the group most suited to supervise the company's management and limit agency costs³⁴ thereby maximising its efficiency. Under this contractual model, company stakeholders are not the concern of company law as their interests are protected by 1) their contracts to which they have voluntarily agreed and 2) other areas of law³⁵ while broader social issues such as environmental

²⁸ I refer here to the fact that the core legal characteristics of the company have converged across common law and continental European jurisdictions. There are, of course, differences in the traditions of common law jurisdictions, continental European jurisdictions and the company law of the EU.

²⁹ This argument is more forcefully set out in F. Easterbrook and D. Fischel, *The Economic Structure of Corporate Law* (HUP, 1991), Particularly at 7-10 noting that company law, for the most part, provides a framework that parties would select privately through contract but at a greater cost.

³⁰ See R. Posner, *The Economic Analysis of Law*, 8th edn. (Wolters Kluwer, 2010), 14-17.

³¹ M. Friedman, 'The Social Responsibility of Business is to Increase Its Profits' New York Times (September 1970) available at <https://www.nytimes.com/1970/09/13/archives/a-friedman-doctrine-the-social-responsibility-of-business-is-to.html>. Hayek expressed similar sentiments in F. Hayek, 'The Corporation in a Democratic Society: In Whose Interest Ought It and Will it be Run?' in *Business Strategy* (Penguin, 1969) 265-267.

³² Meaning that advancing the interests of shareholders should be objective of the company.

³³ Easterbrook and Fischel, *The Economic Structure of Corporate Law* (n 29), 36-39.

³⁴ Agency costs referring to the potential for company directors to be negligent, opportunistic or wasteful. See M. Jensen and W. Meckling, 'Theory of the Firm: Managerial Behaviour, Agency Costs and Ownership Structure' (1976) 3 *Journal of Economics* 305.

³⁵ For example, by contract law, employment law or insolvency law.

damage and human rights abuses are best addressed by sector specific regulation.³⁶ This theory has been highly influential and can explain most of the core principles of company law. Traditionally, the EU has closely adhered to this theory, the focus of its company law³⁷ being to facilitate business in the single market while at the same time becoming the world's leading regulator of companies in specific contexts.³⁸

The core of European company law lies in upholding the freedom of establishment, which refers to the ability of nationals and companies of Member States being able to freely pursue economic activity in other Member States.³⁹ This freedom is crucial to give effect to the four fundamental freedoms of the single market, namely free movement of goods, people, services and capital.⁴⁰ Hence, the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) prohibits 'restrictions on the freedom of establishment of nationals of a Member State in the territory of another Member State'.⁴¹ The TFEU also provides that, for the purposes of freedom of establishment, 'companies or firms' shall be treated in the same way as nationals of Member States.⁴² The pursuit of this freedom of establishment has resulted in three core principles of European company law being developed over time: I) harmonisation, II) negative integration and III) enabling cross border trade.

I) *Harmonisation*

The earliest concern regarding the freedom of establishment was that differences between the company law of Member States could limit the development of the single market.⁴³ Hence, a consensus emerged that a degree of company law harmonisation was necessary to allow companies to freely and easily establish themselves in different Member States.⁴⁴ The other rationale for harmonisation was the potential effects of 'regulatory competition' whereby Member States would reform their company law to attract business to their jurisdiction.⁴⁵ In other words, there was a concern that an EU Delaware might emerge which could imbalance

³⁶ For example, environmental law or tort law.

³⁷ European company law operates alongside the national company law of Member States and so there is no complete companies Act or Code. Rather, European company law operates as a second layer of company law that prevails over the national company law of Member States but covers a relatively small number of areas.

³⁸ Obvious examples being in the contexts of employment law, privacy law and digital services.

³⁹ The Freedom of establishment has been defined by the ECJ in *R v Secretary of State for Transport, ex p Factorame* [1991] ECR I-3905 as 'the actual pursuit of economic activity through a fixed establishment in another Member State for indefinite periods', at [20]. See also Case C-55/94 *Gebhard v Consiglio dell'Ordine degli Avvocati e Procuratori di Milano* ECLI:EU:C:1995:411 [1995] ECR I-4165 which defined freedom of establishment as the participation 'on a stable and continuous basis, in the economic life of a Member State other than his State of origin', [25].

⁴⁰ See C. Barnard, *The Substantive Law of the EU: The Four Freedoms* (OUP, 2022).

⁴¹ TFEU, art 49.

⁴² *Ibid*, art 54.

⁴³ See J. Armour and W.G. Ringe, 'European Company Law 1999–2010: Renaissance and Crisis' (2011) 48 *Common Market Law Review* 125, 129–31 highlighting that different rules may require companies to change or develop new business frameworks thereby increasing the cost of cross-border business.

⁴⁴ N. De Luca, *European Company Law*, 2nd edn (CUP, 2021), 17.

⁴⁵ See D. Murphy, *The Structure of Regulatory Competition* (OUP, 2004).

the single market and/or lead to a ‘race to the bottom’ and the erosion of shareholder and creditor rights.⁴⁶

Article 50 of the TFEU provides the legal basis for the harmonisation of European company law by stating that the European Parliament and Council will approve Directives to achieve freedom of establishment ‘by coordinating to the necessary extent the safeguards which, for the protection of the interests *of members and others*, are required by Member States of companies or firms ... with a view to making such safeguards *equivalent* throughout the Union’.⁴⁷ Rather than attempting to create ‘equivalence’ via an entire European company law code, a basic level of harmonisation was introduced through a series of company law Directives.⁴⁸ Between 1968 and 1989, eight company law Directives were introduced, creating a common framework on issues such as the disclosure of company documents, the merger and division of companies and rules around accounting and auditing.⁴⁹ In the 1990’s the process of harmonisation slowed, primarily due to a failure to find agreement around more ambitious company law harmonisation.⁵⁰ For instance, agreement could not be reached on the fifth company law Directive on employee representation on company boards and the ninth Directive on a common framework for corporate groups.⁵¹ This difficulty was exacerbated by enlargement, particularly the accession of the UK and Ireland who as common law jurisdictions had significantly different traditions regarding company law compared to the continental European states.⁵² A further factor was the principle of subsidiarity introduced in the Maastricht Treaty which provides that the EU should refrain from legislative intervention unless such intervention can be more effective than national rules.⁵³ Harmonisation initiatives aimed at preventing deregulation did not align with the subsidiarity principle.

II) *Negative Integration*

In the 1990s, developments in European company law came primarily from the courts through a series of judgments on ‘negative integration’⁵⁴ i.e. the invalidation of Member State rules

⁴⁶ See L. Enriques, ‘EC Company Law and the Fears of a European Delaware’ (2004) 15 *European Business Law Review* 1259 and M Gelter, ‘The Structure of Regulatory Competition in European Corporate Law’ (2005) 5 *Journal of Corporate Law Studies* 247.

⁴⁷ Emphasis added.

⁴⁸ See L. Enriques, ‘A Harmonized European Company law: Are We There Already?’ (2017) 66(3) *International and Comparative Law Quarterly* 763.

⁴⁹ Many of these Directives have been amended and now form part of the consolidating Directive (EU) 2017/1132 [2017] OJ L 169/46. For a full discussion see N. De Luca, *European Company Law* (n 44).

⁵⁰ Most notably, the fifth company law Directive on employee representation and the ninth Directive on a common framework for corporate groups failed to be enacted into law.

⁵¹ This was despite several reformulations of these Directives. See J. Du Plessis and J. Dine, ‘The Fate of the Draft Fifth Directive on Company Law: Accommodation instead of Harmonisation’ (1997) *Journal of Business Law* 23 and K. Bohlhoff and J. Budde, ‘Company Groups - The EEC Proposal for a Ninth Directive in the Light of the Legal Situation in the Federal Republic of Germany’ (1984) 6 *Journal of Comparative Business and Capital Market Law* 163.

⁵² Particularly in relation to employee representation and the structures of corporate management. See Armour and Ringe, ‘European Company Law 1999–2010’ (n 43) 128–29.

⁵³ See F. Fabbrini, ‘The Principle of Subsidiarity’ in R. Schütze and T. Tridimas (eds), *Oxford Principles of European Union Law* (Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2018).

⁵⁴ See Art. 26(2) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union describing a common market ‘characterized by the abolition, as between Member States, of obstacles to the free movement of goods, persons, services and capital’.

which limited the freedom of establishment. A significant issue in transnational company law is how should the jurisdictional location of a company be determined.⁵⁵ Certain countries, including the UK, Ireland and the Netherlands (as well as all US states) follow an ‘incorporation’ approach whereby a company’s location is where it is legally registered regardless of where it conducts the majority of its business. The alternative approach is for a company’s location to be determined by its main centre of operations or ‘real seat’,⁵⁶ an approach followed by most EU Member States including Germany, France and Italy. Under the real seat approach, a company legally formed and registered in, for example, Spain that had its primary centre of business in France would be regarded as a French organisation but not as a company as it had not been registered under French law. Accordingly, the company would have no legal personality, potentially lose its ability to enforce its rights while its shareholders could become personally responsible for the company’s debts. The ‘real seat’ doctrine was effectively a restriction on cross-border business as companies feared conducting substantial operations in a real seat jurisdiction as it may be determined that their main centre of operation was located there. Hence, the real seat approach was at odds with freedom of establishment as, fundamentally, it amounted to a refusal to recognise the validity of a legally formed company from one Member State attempting to establish itself in another Member State.

A series of high-profile ECJ decisions continually regarded the real seat approach as invalid under the treaty provisions on freedom of establishment. Perhaps the most well-known of these cases is the *Centros*⁵⁷ decision, which was followed by other high profile judgments in *Inspire Art*,⁵⁸ *Sevic*,⁵⁹ and *Überseeing*.⁶⁰ The legal effect of these decisions was that Member States must recognise the validity of companies from other Member States and effectively marked the end of the real seat approach to corporate jurisdiction within the EU.

III) *Enabling Cross Border Trade*

In the early 2000s, the EU again focused on developing company law, this time to more directly facilitate cross border business. The first example of this was the creation of new forms of business organisation that could transcend national borders which led to the introduction of the European Economic Interest Grouping (EEIG)⁶¹ and the *Societas Europaea (SE)*.⁶² However, it is important to note that these business organisations remain rooted in national law, for

⁵⁵ See W. Ebke, ‘The European Conflict-of-Corporate-Laws Revolution: *Überseeing*, *Inspire Art* and Beyond’ (2005) 16(1) *European Business Law Review* 9.

⁵⁶ See K. Baelz and T. Baldwin, ‘The End of the Real Seat Theory (Sitztheorie)’ (2002) 3(12) *German Law Journal* 8.

⁵⁷ Case C-212/97 *Centros Ltd v. Erhvervs-og Selskabsstyrelsen* [1999] ECR I-1459.

⁵⁸ Case C-167/01 *Kamer van Koophandel en Fabrieken voor Amsterdam v Inspire Art Ltd* [2003] ECR I-10155.

⁵⁹ Case C-411/03 *Sevic Systems AG* ECLI:EU:C:2005:762, [2005] ECR I-10805.

⁶⁰ Case C-208/00 *Überseeing BV v Nordic Construction Company Baumanagement GmbH* [2002] ECR I-9919.

⁶¹ Council Regulation (EEC) 2137/85 [1985] OJ L 199/1.

⁶² Council Regulation (EC) 2157/2001 [2001] OJ L 294/1.

example, the *SE* must have its a registered office in the Member State and is governed by the law of that jurisdiction for the many matters not covered by the *SE* Regulation.⁶³

A series of Directives were also introduced including on cross border takeovers,⁶⁴ Cross-Border Mergers⁶⁵ and on Shareholder Rights.⁶⁶ This period was heavily influenced by a report by the High Level Group of Company Law Experts ('the Expert Group')⁶⁷ whose vision was that European company law 'should provide a flexible framework'⁶⁸ and should not be used for regulatory purposes.⁶⁹ In its 'Plan to Move Forward',⁷⁰ the Commission, in agreeing with the Expert Group, emphasised the importance of 'fostering efficiency and competitiveness of business',⁷¹ the ultimate aim being economic growth and job creation.⁷² In accordance with this vision, the enacted Directives provided a large degree of flexibility for companies and represented a 'minimalist' and enabling approach to company law rather than a regulatory one.⁷³

This section has shown how European company law has developed around the core idea of facilitating business in the single market by advancing the principles of freedom of establishment. This led to Luca Enriques, in 2006 and again in 2017, to describe European company law as 'trivial'⁷⁴ in the sense that it did not impact how companies were 'directed, managed and controlled'.⁷⁵ However, the EU's position began to change in 2018 with the publication of the European Green deal.

2) Corporate Sustainability

The theory set out at the start of section 1 is undoubtedly the default theory guiding the development of company law, however, it has two fundamental shortcomings. The first is that, as many authors have pointed out, the nexus of contracts model rests on faulty descriptions of

⁶³ Article 63 of the *SE* Regulation states that matters such as winding up and insolvency are governed by the applicable national law.

⁶⁴ Directive 2004/25/EC [2004] OJ L 142/12.

⁶⁵ Directive 2005/56/EC [2005] OJ L 310/1.

⁶⁶ Directive 2007/36/EC [2007] OJ L 184/17.

⁶⁷ High Level Group of Company Law Experts, *A Modern Regulatory Framework for Company Law in Europe* (2002) available at www.ecgi.global/sites/default/files/report_en.pdf.

⁶⁸ *ibid* 5.

⁶⁹ *ibid*, 36 stating 'If we consider that, in company law regulation, it is important to provide for a framework for competitive business, this calls for flexible rules and forms of rulemaking, for light regulatory regimes where possible, scope for party autonomy and for less cumbersome and burdensome procedures'. The group did however advocate for increased regulation through disclosures at 45–47.

⁷⁰ European Commission, *Modernising Company Law* (2003) available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=celex%3A52003DC0284>.

⁷¹ *ibid* 3 and 9.

⁷² *ibid* 9.

⁷³ Armour and Ringe, 'European Company Law 1999–2010' (n 43), 150.

⁷⁴ L. Enriques, 'EC Company Law Directives and Regulations: How Trivial Are They?' (2006) 27 *University of Pennsylvania Journal of International Economic Law* 1. He reiterated the point again in 2017, see Enriques, 'A Harmonized European Company law' (n 48).

⁷⁵ Enriques, 'EC Company Law Directives' (n 74), 7. Enriques did admit certain exceptions to his triviality thesis, mainly in relation to certain accounting rules.

the company.⁷⁶ Many alternative models highlight these inaccurate descriptions by emphasising the company's non-contractual dimensions such as the importance of the state in a company's creation and ongoing recognition⁷⁷ or the company's sociological⁷⁸ or legal⁷⁹ characteristics.⁸⁰ The second shortcoming is the harms that continue to arise from the operation of companies,⁸¹ particularly in a transnational context where business is organised through corporate groups⁸² or chains of companies.⁸³ Some examples include dangerous working conditions for employees,⁸⁴ child labour⁸⁵ and environmental damage.⁸⁶ Such issues seem incapable of being addressed solely through a patchwork of regulatory law. As companies obtain increasing levels of power, operate globally and extend their reach into all aspects of society, it becomes increasingly difficult for sector specific regulation to address all contexts where a pursuit of shareholder value generates negative externalities and should be constrained for the benefit of society. In other words, as society and companies have become more complex and globalised, it has become more difficult for sector specific regulation to limit the harms of business.

These issues prompted the EU to begin to reform its company law and go beyond the classical division between 'facilitative' areas of law on one hand and 'regulatory' areas of law on the other.⁸⁷ What distinguishes company law from external regulation is its ability to alter and shift the dynamics within companies. However, changes to company law also have the potential to inhibit the ability of company as an institution to contribute to economic development. Hence, the EU did not attempt to alter the company's core characteristics,⁸⁸ which form the basis for

⁷⁶ For example, the characterisation of shareholders as having homogenous interests and sharing a singular focus in maximising the residual, see M. Hayden and M. Bodie, *Reconstructing the Corporation: From Shareholder Primacy to Shared Governance* (2020, CUP).

⁷⁷ See S. Watson, 'The Corporate Legal Person' (2019) 19(1) *Journal of Corporate Law Studies* 137.

⁷⁸ See E. Micheler, *Company Law: A Real Entity Theory* (OUP, 2021).

⁷⁹ See A. Keay, *The Corporate Objective: Corporations, Globalisation and the Law* (Elgar, 2011).

⁸⁰ I do not enter the complex debate on the theory of the firm in this working paper. I do explore it *The Societal Company*, chapter 1 (n 1).

⁸¹ For a report setting out many such examples see British Institute of International and Comparative Law, 'Study on Due Diligence Requirements Through the Supply Chain' (2020) available at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/8ba0a8fd-4c83-11ea-b8b7-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>. The report also provides examples of companies reducing their negative environmental and human rights record.

⁸² Where one 'parent' company owns shares in multiple other 'subsidiary' companies. See P. Underwood, *Corporate Group Legitimacy: Reconceptualising the Corporate Group* (Routledge, 2024).

⁸³ Which operate through contractual governance and codes of conduct. See A. Beckers, *Enforcing Corporate Social Responsibility Codes on Global Self-Regulation and National Private Law* (2018, Hart Publishing).

⁸⁴ One notable example being the Rana Plaza disaster in building in Dhaka, Bangladesh where a building used to manufacture garments collapsed killing more than 1,100 and injuring over 2,500 persons see International Labour Organization, *The Rana Plaza disaster ten years on: What has changed?* (2023) available at <https://webapps.ilo.org/infostories/en-GB/Stories/Country-Focus/rana-plaza#intro>.

⁸⁵ For example, where children are used in the mining of cobalt. See Amnesty International, 'Human Rights Abuses in the Democratic Republic of the Congo Power the Global Trade in Cobalt' (2016) available at: <https://www.amnesty.org/download/Documents/AFR6231832016ENGLISH.PDF>.

⁸⁶ For example through pollution or contribution to climate change. See Amnesty International, *The Cost Of Doing Business?: The Petrochemical Industry's Toxic Pollution In The USA* (2024) available at <https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/AMR51/7566/2024/en/>

⁸⁷ For a broad discussion on this point see D. Hess, 'Social Reporting: A Reflexive Law Approach to Corporate Social Responsiveness' (1999) 25 *The Journal of Corporation Law* 41.

⁸⁸ I refer here to the fundamental characteristics of the company that exist across almost all jurisdictions as described in R. Kraakman et al, *The Anatomy of Corporate Law: A Comparative and Functional Approach* 3rd edn. (OUP, 2017), 5-15 as

its efficiency and productivity but rather looked to new procedural rules around sustainability reporting and due diligence.

Sustainability has long been a part of the European project with Article 3(3) of the TFEU stating that the EU will work toward ‘sustainable development of Europe’ and Article 5 providing that the EU ‘shall contribute to peace, security, the sustainable development of the Earth’. The European Green Deal, for the first time,⁸⁹ made a link between sustainability and company law by stating that sustainability should be ‘embedded into the corporate governance framework’.⁹⁰ A series of reports mentioned above ultimately led to a suite of legislative initiatives focused on advancing corporate sustainability starting with the SFDR in 2019⁹¹ followed by the CSRD in 2022 and the CSDDD in 2024, the CRSD and CSDDD being the most relevant from a company law perspective.

The CSRD,⁹² requires certain large companies to publish information about their impact on sustainability related issues such as human rights and environmental matters. Such types of disclosure have long been viewed as a useful tool in developing socially responsible business and many companies voluntarily report information on such matters.⁹³ However, the difficulty with voluntary disclosures is the incentives that exist for companies to selectively report information (cherry picking),⁹⁴ report false information (greenwashing)⁹⁵ or produce vacuous reports with non-material information (boiler plate reporting). The primary significance of the CSRD was its imposition of mandatory disclosures to be prepared in accordance with detailed standards⁹⁶ and were to be audited. The core idea was that mandatory reporting rules would increase the accuracy and comparability of reports and that companies would take steps to reduce their negative externalities in order to have positive, reputation enhancing information available to report.⁹⁷

The other major development was the CSDDD⁹⁸ which imposes a positive obligation on companies to identify actual and potential adverse human rights and environmental impacts

being 1) legal personality 2) limited liability of shareholders 3) transferable shares 4) delegated management to a board of directors 5) Shareholders having ultimate control and access to net earnings.

⁸⁹ There were some references to sustainability in European company law before this, most notably in the Non-financial Reporting Directive 2014/95/EU.

⁹⁰ The European Green Deal (n 5), [2.2.1].

⁹¹ Regulation (EU) 2019/2088 [2019] OJ L 317/1 which aimed to harness private funding to enable the transition to a net-zero economy by increasing transparency on the sustainability of financial products allowing ESG orientated investors to select companies and projects which support sustainability related activities.

⁹² CSRD (n 13).

⁹³ See KPMG, ‘Key Global Trends in Sustainability Reporting’ (2022) available at <https://kpmg.com/xx/en/our-insights/esg/survey-of-sustainability-reporting-2022/global-trends.html>.

⁹⁴ See D. Ahern, ‘Turning Up the Heat? EU Sustainability Goals and the Role of Reporting under the Non-Financial Reporting Directive’ (2016) 4 *European Company and Financial Law Review* 599 noting that companies, left to their own devices, are inclined ‘to report favourable aspects than less favourable aspects of their activities and policies.’

⁹⁵ See E. Yu, B. Lu, and C. Chen, ‘Greenwashing in Environmental, Social and Governance Disclosures’ (2020) 52 *Research in International Business and Finance* 1.

⁹⁶ The CSRD delegates the details of what must be reported to the European Sustainability Reporting Standards available at [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=PI_COM:C\(2023\)5303](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=PI_COM:C(2023)5303).

⁹⁷ For a comprehensive analysis of European sustainability reporting see D. Monciardini, *Regulating EU Sustainability Reporting: Learning from Failure and Success* (CUP, 2025).

⁹⁸ CSDDD (n 14).

arising from their subsidiaries and contractual partners and to take steps to end or minimise those impacts. It requires companies to prepare a due diligence policy and code of conduct.⁹⁹ Companies would then be required to seek contractual assurances from its subsidiaries and business partners that they will comply with these codes and policies and oversee compliance. Compliance was also to be conducted by national supervisory authorities¹⁰⁰ and a European Network of Supervisory Authorities.¹⁰¹ The CSDDD also included civil liability provisions where a company ‘intentionally or negligently’ failed to comply with its due diligence obligations and that the failure caused damage to a person’s legal interest under national law.¹⁰² The CSDDD had extraterritorial effects by applying to companies registered outside the EU if they meet the turnover threshold from business conducted inside the EU.¹⁰³ More significantly, once a company fell within the CSDDD’s scope, their due diligence obligations applied to all its subsidiaries and business partners, regardless of their size or geographical location.¹⁰⁴ The CSDDD’s significance was its potential to develop a framework of legal accountability that would apply across entire supply chains and corporate groups,¹⁰⁵ transcending jurisdictional boundaries and the assumption that every company is a separate unit of rights and liabilities.

The EU’s approach to company law reform was novel in its imposition of procedural rules designed to reduce the global negative externalities of business. The rules had the potential to 1) increase awareness within the company of its external effects; 2) provide practical guidance on how companies can mitigate or end their negative externalities; 3) harness the importance of a company’s reputation and 4) establish direct links and open communication channels with stakeholders and other parties affected by a company’s activities. From a theoretical perspective, it showed a shift from a facilitative approach to one grounded in reflexive law. Reflexive law¹⁰⁶ has its foundations in systems theory which views society as being comprised of differentiated systems that are ‘self-referential’ in the sense that they function according to their own logic, values, norms, and language.¹⁰⁷ Reflexive law, rather than imposing rules from one system (the legal system) on to another (the economic system and its subsystems of companies), looks to law’s ability to structure processes and procedures within systems to make them responsive to outside interests. In a company law context, procedural rules prevent companies from operating as closed systems singularly focused on shareholder value/profit¹⁰⁸

⁹⁹ Ibid, Art. 5.

¹⁰⁰ Ibid Art. 24.

¹⁰¹ Ibid Art. 28.

¹⁰² Ibid, Art 27.

¹⁰³ Ibid Art. 2(2).

¹⁰⁴ For a discussion regarding the CSDDD’s potential effects on US companies see L. Enriques, M. Gatti and R. Shapira ‘How the EU’s Sustainability Due Diligence Directive Could Reshape Corporate America’ (2025) *European Corporate Governance Institute Working Paper* available at <https://www.ecgi.global/publications/working-papers/how-the-eus-sustainability-due-diligence-directive-could-reshape>.

¹⁰⁵ For a broader discussion of liability in supply chains see J. Quinn and R. Condon, ‘Beyond the Individual-Company: From Corporate Social Responsibilities to Corporate Social Liability’ (2025) 16 *Transnational Legal Theory* 226.

¹⁰⁶ G. Teubner, ‘Substantive and Reflexive Elements in Modern Law’ (1983) 17(2) *Law and Society Review* 239.

¹⁰⁷ See G. Teubner, ‘After Legal Instrumentalism? Strategic Models of Post-Regulatory Law’ (1984) *European University Institute Working Papers* available at <https://cadmus.eui.eu/handle/1814/23192>.

¹⁰⁸ See Teubner, ‘Substantive and Reflexive Elements’ (n 108), 276-278.

and instead stimulate their internal resources in a way that develops ‘economic self-restraint’ regarding actions which cause harm to the non-economic environment.¹⁰⁹ Hence, reflexive law is not directed toward goal-oriented intervention and so does not seek to directly prescribe managerial decision making nor alter the company’s core characteristics. Instead, it recognises the many different types of companies, the complexity of the challenges they face and the need for the autonomy to respond to their unique situations.¹¹⁰ However, it also does not leave the regulation of companies to external rules and instead relies on mandatory processes to make the company’s management responsive to its external effects. Yet, despite the EU’s corporate sustainability rules broadly taking a reflexive approach, they still became viewed as excessively regulatory and overly complex.

3) A Return to Competitiveness

Starting in 2024, the EU, faced with an array of local and global challenges, refocused its policy priorities and once again put competitiveness and the single market at the heart of the EU agenda.¹¹¹ This return to a policy focus on economic productivity and competitiveness led to the European Commission’s 2025 Omnibus I Proposal¹¹² which set out to simplify the corporate sustainability framework. A final agreement on the Omnibus was reached between the European Parliament and EU Member States on December 8th 2025¹¹³ which significantly alters both the CSRD and CSDDD.¹¹⁴ Regarding the CSRD, the Omnibus will raise the applicable thresholds, taking approximately 80% of companies out of the CSRD’s scope. There is also a simplified accompanying standard meaning that the companies remaining within the CSRD’s scope will be subject to less detailed reporting obligations.¹¹⁵ Regarding the CSDDD, again, the thresholds were significantly raised removing many companies from its scope.¹¹⁶ For companies remaining in scope, the requirements will extend only to 1st tier contractual partners only, rather than the entire supply chain which will significantly lower its extraterritorial effects. The civil liability model is also to be entirely removed.

One of the major lessons to be drawn from the finalisation of the Omnibus is that reform to European company law and corporate governance continues to be fractious. The policy landscape has fundamentally shifted as the EU faces new challenges and European company law has found itself at the faultline of this shifting terrain. Despite the EU broadly taking a reflexive approach to sustainability orientated rules, the framework still became subject to

¹⁰⁹ G. Teubner, ‘Corporate Fiduciary Duties and their Beneficiaries’ in G. Teubner and K. Hopt (eds), *Corporate Governance and Directors’ Liabilities: Legal, Economic and Sociological Analyses on Corporate Social Responsibility* (De Gruyter, 1985), 164-165.

¹¹⁰ A. Johnston, ‘Integrating Sustainability into Corporate Governance’ in C. Bruner and M. Moore (eds) *A Research Agenda for Corporate Law* (Elgar Publishing, 2023), 57.

¹¹¹ As emphasised by the Letta (n 19) and Draghi (n 20) reports as well as the Competitiveness Compass (n 25).

¹¹² European Commission, ‘Omnibus I’ (2025) available at https://commission.europa.eu/publications/omnibus-i_en.

¹¹³ See https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/de/ip_25_2981.

¹¹⁴ The omnibus now awaits formal approval from both the European Parliament and the Council.

¹¹⁵ European Financial Reporting Advisory Group, Draft Simplified European Sustainability Reporting Standards available at <https://www.efrag.org/en/draft-simplified-esrs>.

¹¹⁶ It will now apply to companies with 5,000 employees and a net turnover threshold of EUR 1.5 billion.

extensive opposition ultimately leading to the Omnibus reforms which remove many companies from the scope of the sustainability Directives and reduces the compliance burden. Hence, the Omnibus should not only be viewed as providing simplification but also deregulation. Yet, as noted in both the Letta and Draghi reports, and emphasised by the Jean Monnet Network PROSPER's Shadow Committee on EU Economic Affairs,¹¹⁷ deregulation is not in itself a strategy.

It is against this backdrop that initiatives such as the 28th regime become central to advancing the EU's overall objective of economic competitiveness.¹¹⁸ The express aim of the 28th Regime is to simplify regulation, reduce costs¹¹⁹ and advance freedom of establishment within the single market as the fragmentation of company law rules at Member State level continue to present obstacles for companies.¹²⁰ However, similar initiatives have been attempted before with limited success, most notably the proposal for a European Private company, the *Societas Privata Europaea* (*SPE*), first introduced in 2008 was withdrawn in 2014. The SPE was replaced by a proposal for another type of European company, the *Societas Unius Personae*, which also has not been enacted into law.¹²¹ As mentioned above, the main form of European company, the *SE*, remains thoroughly a creature of national law and offers only minimal advantages over national companies that establish branches in other EU Member States. The difficulty in creating a truly European company again points to the problems that the EU has had with the reform of its company law, which date right back to the fifth company law Directive in the 1980s. Given this history, it is certain that the 28th regime will encounter challenges,¹²² but these challenges must be overcome given the regime's centrality to the EU's competitiveness plan.

Conclusion

As the EU continues to search for the appropriate balance between regulation and the facilitation of business, European company law is rapidly evolving. The Omnibus will significantly alter the corporate sustainability framework and indicates a return to more traditional ideas regarding the role of company law in society. As the Commission turns its attention to positive strategies to boost competitiveness, in a company law context through the

¹¹⁷ The Jean Monnet Network PROSPER (Project to Research Opportunities to Strengthen Prosperity and Economic Resilience in the EU) is coordinated by the Dublin City University Brexit Institute & Dublin European Law Institute under the lead of Prof. Federico Fabbrini. The statement from the Network's Shadow Committee on EU Economic Affairs is available at <https://prospernetwork.eu/the-eu-needs-to-accelerate-the-implementation-of-the-letta-draghi-agenda-statement/>

¹¹⁸ See [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2025/779233/EPRS_BRI\(2025\)779233_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2025/779233/EPRS_BRI(2025)779233_EN.pdf)

¹¹⁹ The Competitiveness Compass (n 25), 4.

¹²⁰ For example, the EU Startup and Scaleup Strategy recognises that regulatory fragmentation remains a major barrier to scaling across borders (e.g. non-transferable company forms, variable insolvency procedures, inconsistent employee participation rules), which increase transaction costs and deter international expansion available at https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/jobs-and-economy/eu-startup-and-scaleup-strategy_en

¹²¹ De Luca, *European Company Law* (n 44), 64-74.

¹²² Such challenges may take the form of reluctance within Member States to relinquish competency over the regulation of companies and potential opposition based around the erosion of shareholder, creditor or employee rights. For example, on the last point see The European Trade Union Institute, How a 28th company law regime jeopardises workers' rights available at <https://www.etui.org/publications/how-28th-company-law-regime-jeopardises-workers-rights>.

proposed 28th regime, history warns that such initiatives will be difficult to finalise. The Commission's legislative draft of the 28th regime is expected in Q1 2026 and will prove to be a key indicator for the implementation of the Letta and Draghi reports and the Competitiveness Compass.